

NOVEL CARBON FIBER SURFACE TREATMENT WITH ULTRAVIOLET LIGHT IN OZONE TO PROMOTE COMPOSITE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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SUMMARY

A novel technique employing ultraviolet (UV) light in the presence of ozone (UVO) was used for surface treating carbon fibers. After UVO treatment, a PAN based carbon fiber had increased surface oxygen concentration, increased fiber tensile strength, and increased adhesion with an epoxy matrix. The beneficial effects of this surface treatment for carbon fibers were investigated.

Key words: surface treatment, fiber, ozone, ultraviolet light, composites, adhesion

CARBON FIBER SURFACE TREATMENT

Carbon fibers require surface treatment to establish suitable adhesion to polymeric matrices. In general these surface treatments are classified in three categories: anodic oxidation, a wet process where solution concentration and amperage must be maintained; exposure to ozone gas at elevated temperature; and treatment in caustic solutions such as nitric acid. Surface treatments produce improved composite properties through a two part mechanism. First, a weak, defect-laden outer layer is removed from the carbon fiber surface, resulting in a stronger surface to sustain shear loading. The second contribution of surface treatments is the deposition of chemical functionalities, most notably oxygen containing moieties, which improve wetting and bonding between the fiber and matrix [1].

This work describes a fast, inexpensive and environmentally benign process requiring only ultraviolet light and ozone (UVO) for the surface treatment (oxidation) of reinforcing fibers. The basis of the UVO method is the application of high intensity ultraviolet light in the presence of ozone [2,3]. The ultraviolet light interacts with ozone to create oxygen radicals that react with the fibers. Additionally, the energetic ultraviolet light can directly interact with the fiber surface to disrupt and change chemical bonds creating favorable conditions to react with the gaseous oxygen radicals. The result of the UVO process is the rapid oxygenation of the carbon fiber surface, which is beneficial to fiber wetting by the matrix, adhesion, and fiber-matrix bonding. Furthermore, this method does not require any chemicals, is conducted at room temperature, and can be accomplished very quickly.

Carbon fibers made from polyacrylonitrile and pitch were used to demonstrate the efficacy of the new method. Changes in fiber surface chemistry following treatment were evaluated by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. Fiber surface topography and roughness were evaluated using scanning tunneling microscopy and the effect of UVO treatment on single fiber tensile strength was measured. A single fiber fragmentation test was used to measure the interfacial shear strength to an epoxy matrix.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL

Carbon fibers from 2 different precursors were obtained from the manufacturer in their “as received” state without any surface treatment. AU4 (Hexcel) is derived from polyacrylonitrile (PAN), with a tensile modulus of 228 GPa. AS4 is the surface treated analog to AU4, and has been given an anodic oxidative treatment by the manufacturer. In some cases, data on AS4 is presented for comparison to the AU4 treated with the UV-Ozone method. The other fiber evaluated in this study was derived from coal tar pitch (PITCH), Dialead K63712 (Mitsubishi Chemical), and has a modulus of 634 GPa. The PAN and PITCH fibers were exposed to ultraviolet light in the presence of ozone. The source of the UV flux was a pulsed Xenon flash lamp. Approximately 700 ppm of ozone was passed over the sample during UV irradiation.

XPS measurements were performed using a Physical Electronics PHI-5400 ESCA work station. X-Ray photons were generated from a polychromatic Mg anode (1254 eV). The analyzer was operated in the fixed energy mode employing a pass energy of 89.45 eV for survey scans and 17.9 eV for utility scans.

Low current STM images were collected in constant current mode using a Nanoscope IV Multimode SPM (Digital Instruments, Santa Barbara, CA) equipped with an E scanner. Images were collected at ambient temperature and pressure using platinum-iridium 8mm length tips. Multiple fibers were evaluated to obtain a representative collection of images of each fiber type. Two surface measurements were collected on the image set for each fiber type. R_q is the root mean square of the Z values within a given area, and R_a is the arithmetic average of the deviations from the center plane.

To evaluate the effect of UV-Ozone (UVO) treatments on fiber mechanical properties, tensile strength measurements were conducted on single filaments of “As Received” and UVO treated fibers. The test method was in general compliance with ASTM D3379 (now retired). Single filaments were mounted on paper tabs to form test specimens with a one or two inch gage length. The fiber diameter was measured using optical microscopy or a laser micrometer system. Tensile loads were collected using a one pound load cell at a crosshead displacement rate of 0.02 inches per minute. A minimum of 20 filaments were tested to characterize each fiber type.

The single fiber fragmentation test provides a sensitive means to quantify the interfacial shear strength of continuous fibers in a polymeric matrix. In practice, a single filament, such as a carbon fiber, is axially aligned in a micro-tensile coupon as illustrated in Figure 2. The test specimen is loaded in tension which causes shear stresses to develop between the rigid fiber and the comparatively lower modulus polymer. Under tensile load, the shear forces will exceed the tensile strength of the encapsulated fiber and the fiber will fail within the coupon. With continued loading, the fragmentation process is repeated until the fiber is rendered to a characteristic aspect ratio. The aspect ratio is an indicator of the level of adhesion between the fiber and polymer. Fibers with low

adhesion will have longer aspect ratios than fibers with greater adhesion, when all other factors are held constant. The interfacial shear strength, τ , is calculated using a shear lag analysis [4] by the relationship

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_f d}{2l_c} \quad (1)$$

where σ_f is the fiber tensile strength, d is the fiber diameter, and l_c is the experimentally determined fiber critical length. An additional benefit of the fragmentation test is the ability to observe the fragmentation process using optical microscopy. The use of polarized light microscopy can be used to qualitatively assess the failure mode of the fiber-matrix system. Details for conducting this test can be found elsewhere [5,6]. The matrix was diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A, Epon 828 (Resolution Performance Products, Houston, TX) cured with a stoichiometric amount (14.5 g/100 g resin) of m-phenylene diamine (Sigma-Aldrich Corp., St. Louis, MO). A schedule of 2 h at 75 °C followed by 2 h at 125 °C was used to process the single fiber fragmentation coupons. Each coupon was examined using transmitted optical microscopy to verify fiber alignment and overall quality.

RESULTS

The surface of the untreated “as received” AU4 fibers possessed an O/C ratio of 0.02. Following just 5 seconds of exposure to a UVO treatment this ratio increased to 0.12 (Figure 1). The fibers continued to oxidize with UVO treatment times of up to 90s where it reached a plateau of O/C atomic ratio of 0.22. Exposure to only ozone (green symbols) or to the ultraviolet light alone (red symbols) did not produce the same level of rapid surface oxygenation as did the combination of simultaneous irradiation with the ultraviolet light in the presence of supplemental ozone gas (blue symbols of Figure 1).

Figure 1. Effect of Surface Treatment on O:C Atomic Ratio of AU4 Carbon Fibers.

The highly graphitic as received PITCH fibers had an O/C atomic ratio of 0.02, the same as the untreated AU4 pan fiber. Following 90 sec UVO treatment, the O/C atomic ratio increased to 0.06, much less than the increase achieved in AU4 under the same treatment conditions. The graphitic pitch fibers have fewer lattice edges compared to the AU4 fibers, resulting in less opportunity for oxidation of the fiber surface by the UVO treatment. Scanning tunneling microscopy found the surface roughness of both the PAN and PITCH fibers was slightly increased following UVO treatment (Figure 2).

Surface Roughness

Figure 2. The effect of UVO treatment on carbon fiber surface roughness.

Figure 3. Typical STM images of AU4, AU4+UVO, and AS4 carbon fibers.

Typical STM images for the PAN based fibers are shown in Figure 3. The nodular, graphitic crystallites are more clearly defined in the STM images of AU4+UVO and the commercially treated AS4, with UVO treated fibers having the largest nodular structure. One possibility is that the UVO treatment is removing a weakly bound, incoherent layer on the fiber surface which results in a structurally stronger surface for the development of interfacial bonds.

Tensile strength data from single filaments of untreated AU4 and AU4+UV-Ozone surface treatment are presented in Figure 4. Following treatment, the tensile strength of the AU4+UV-Ozone treated fibers was 11% greater than the baseline AU4 system. The t-test confirms that the difference in tensile strength is statistically significant at the 0.10 probability level. Similar findings have been reported by others [7]. It is also noteworthy that the mean diameter of the UV-Ozone treated fiber is less following UV-Ozone treatment, which suggests that the photo-oxidative process is simultaneously removing material from the fiber surface as well as changing the surface chemistry. From the diameter measurements, it is estimated that 100-300 nm of material is removed during the 90 second treatment used in this study.

Figure 4. Fiber tensile strength following UVO treatment.

Similar improvements in tensile strength were found for the Dialead Pitch fibers following UVO treatment (Figure 4). Following treatment, the tensile strength exhibited a 10.5% improvement. Pitch fibers are inherently weaker than PAN fibers, and the scatter in strength data for high modulus fibers is greater than lower modulus materials. Although the scatter is large, it is apparent that the UVO treatment has not damaged the fiber at the treatment levels used in this study.

Figure 5 shows the changes in interfacial deformation mode of fibers in a fragmentation coupon for the AU4 fibers in an epoxy matrix. The untreated AU4 fiber exhibits a diffuse birefringent pattern that is associated with low levels of adhesion. Following UVO treatment, the AU4-UVO is nearly identical to the commercially surface treated AS4.

Figure 5. Birefringent stress pattern in fragmentation coupons of AU4, AU4+UVO, and AS4.

Figure 6. Birefringent stress pattern in fragmentation coupons of Dialead fiber before and after UVO treatment.

Likewise, the the Dialead coal tar pitch fiber exhibited the same change in failure mechanism. The “as received” pitch fiber had a diffuse birefringent pattern indistinguishable from the untreated AU4 system (Figure 6). Following UVO treatment, the pitch fiber failure mode was observed to be intense and symmetrically distributed along each side of the locus of fiber fracture. This failure mode is indicative of high levels of fiber-matrix adhesion.

The interfacial shear strength calculated from Equation 1 are presented graphically in Figure 7. Using strength values from the single filament tensile measurements, the interfacial shear strength of AU4+UV-Ozone was more than twice the baseline AU4 system. Furthermore, the interfacial shear strength of the AU4+UVO system was greater than the commercially treated AS4 system.

The IFSS for the untreated Pitch fiber, 5.67 MPa, is much lower relative to the PAN fibers (Figure 7, blue bars). After UVO treatment, the IFSS increased nearly 400% to 27.89 MPa, surpassing the commercially treated PAN AS4 fiber. The brief exposure to energetic light in the presence of ozone at room temperature produced a significant increase in the interfacial shear strength in the PAN and Pitch based carbon fibers.

The effect of UVO treatment temperature was investigated for the AU4 system. The UVO treatment was conducted for 90 seconds at room temperature, 35 °C, 45 °C, 60 °C,

and 77 °C. As can be seen in Figure 8, the AU4 surface oxygen increased from nominal 4% to 17% at 35°C. Further increases in oxygen concentration were not found as the process temperature increased to 77°C.

Figure 7. Interfacial shear strength before and after UVO treatment.

Figure 8. Fiber surface oxygen concentration as a function UVO process temperature.

Figure 9. Interfacial shear strength of AU4 fibers following UVO treatment at different process temperatures.

SUMMARY

A new method for the surface treatment of carbon fibers based on ultraviolet irradiation in the presence of ozone was found to be equal or superior to currently practiced methods. Very short treatment times resulted in rapid oxidation of PAN and pitch based fibers while coincidentally removing a defective outer surface. The UVO treatment had the added benefit that it increased the inherent fiber tensile strength. Following UVO treatment the interfacial shear strength was significantly enhanced and surpassed commercial treatments that are now in practice. Additional benefits of the UVO process are that it is conducted at room temperature, can be used on continuous or chopped fibers, does not use caustic solutions or environmentally threatening compounds, and is an inexpensive means to surface treat carbon fibers.

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